

Xylan from Bagasse Hemicellulose*

B. C. Banerjee**, S. Bose, and S. Mukherjee

A xylan has been isolated from the bagasse hemicellulose in the pure and homogeneous state. Hydrolysis of the fully methylated xylan yields 2,3,4-tri-, 2,3-di-, and 2-O-methyl-D-xylopyranose (molar% 2.9, 93.4, and 3.6 respectively). The xylan has been assigned a structure having 70 ± 5 D-xylopyranose units joined together by the 1 $\rightarrow$ 4'- β -glycosidic linkages with a single branch point formed by the 3 $\rightarrow$ 1' union at some point as yet undetermined. These results have been substantiated by the hypiodite and periodate oxidations and also from the study of the degradation products of the periodate-oxidised xylan.

Previous communications^{1,2} on the hemicellulose from bagasse have shown that the hemicellulose is composed of D-xylose, L-arabinose, D-glucose, DL-xyloketose (DL-three-pentulose), and galacturonic acid residues. Repeated failures in isolating an aldobiouronic acid in reasonably sufficient yield by the usual methods^{3,4} from the bagasse hemicellulose suggest that the uronic acid fraction does not play significant role in the main structural features of the bagasse hemicellulose. The very high percentage of D-xylose (83.7%) in the bagasse hemicellulose suggests the polysaccharide to be of the neutral type.

At least a portion of the bagasse hemicellulose, present in the form of a xylan^{4*}, has now been isolated in the pure state. Hydrolysis of the xylan and subsequent estimation of the resulting xylose account for 98.4% of the xylan, comprising exclusively D-xylose. Since β -methylxyloside on hydrolysis loses about 2% xylose⁵, the whole of the polysaccharide has been accounted for as a xylan of at least 99.5% purity.

After methanolysis and hydrolysis of the methylated xylan, the mixture of the methyl sugars furnished spots corresponding to 2,3,4-tri-, 2,3-di-, and 2-O-methyl-D-xylopyranose together with faint spots of an unidentified methylxylose and D-xylose. Quantitative paper chromatography of the mixture and estimation⁶ of the individual methyl sugars indicated the relative molar percentages of the tri-, di- and mono-methylxylose as 2.86, 93.70, and 3.26. The mixture was further separated into pure individual methyl sugars and characterised through their specific rotations and crystalline aniline derivatives. The constituent methylated sugars have thus been confirmed as 2,3,4-tri-, 2,3-di-, and 2-O-methyl-D-xylopyranose (molar% 2.98, 93.1, and 3.93 respectively) together with traces of an unidentified methylxylose and D-xylose, the amounts of which have been neglected. From these results

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**Present address. Dept. of Chemistry, D.A.V. College, Kanpur.

1. Banerjee *et al.*, *Sharkara*, 1960, 3, 125.
2. *Idem*, *Science & Culture*, 1961, 27, 498.
3. Mukherjee and Srivastava, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 2536.
4. Srivastava and Adams, *ibid.*, 1959, 81, 2409.
- 4a. Banerjee *et al.*, *L. J. Sci. Tech.*, 1964, 2, 155.
5. Chanda *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 1289.
6. Hirst *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1949, 928.
7. Hirst and Jones, *ibid.*, 1949, 1059.
8. Ingles and Israel, *ibid.*, 1948, 810.

Incidentally, the xylan from the bagasse hemicellulose bears a close resemblance to the esparto-grass xylan⁵ in having practically the same structural features, the former only showing a slightly lower degree of polymerisation. Since both the plants, sugarcane (*Saccharum officinalis*) and esparto grass (*Stipa tenacissima*) belong to the same botanical family (*Graminae*), it is quite likely that the xylyans occurring in them will have similarity in structures due to the same biogenetic path being followed in their biosynthesis.

EXPERIMENTAL

All specific rotations mentioned are equilibrium values and all the melting points are uncorrected. Unless otherwise stated, all evaporations were carried out *in vacuo* at 45–50°. Paper chromatographic separations were effected by the descending method on Whatman No. 1 and Whatman No. 3 MM filter paper sheets, using the following solvent systems: Solvent A: *n*-butanol-ethanol-water (5:1:4, upper layer); solvent B: *n*-butanol-acetic acid-water (4:1:5, upper layer). The spray reagents used were (a) *p*-anisidine phosphate and (b) ammoniacal silver nitrate. The aniline derivatives of the methylated sugars were prepared by refluxing the sugars in ethanolic aniline for 2 hr.

Isolation of the Xylan.—The hemicellulose (4% KOH fraction) was prepared from bagasse by the method described earlier¹. The crude xylan was isolated as copper complex from the bagasse hemicellulose (18 g.) by three precipitations with Fehling's solution and subsequent treatment with water to remove the soluble polyglucosans⁵. The powdered crude xylan (10 g.) was shaken vigorously for 2 hr. in a beaker containing rectified spirit (250 ml) and HCl (25 ml, conc.). The polysaccharide was filtered, washed with rectified spirit to remove the last traces of the acid, dried, and powdered. It was Soxhletted successively with 50% ethanol, 80% ethanol, rectified spirit, and absolute ethanol (4 hr., each) and dried, when the pure xylan was obtained as a milk-white powder (8 g); sulphated ash 0.33%, pentosans 98.6%. Optical rotation of the xylan could not be determined as it dissolved in NaOH to form a brownish hazy solution.

Hydrolysis of the Xylan and Estimation of Xylose.—(a). The polysaccharide (0.72 g.) was hydrolysed with *N*-H₂SO₄ (125 ml) and the hydrolysate was neutralised (barium carbonate). The clear solution was concentrated (25 ml) and made to 100 ml with water. An aliquot (10 ml) of this solution was taken in a glass-stoppered conical flask and the amount of sugar was estimated by the hypiodite oxidation method⁶. The amount of xylose present in the xylan corresponded to 98.7%.

(b). The xylan (0.046 g.) was hydrolysed and the hydrolysate was transferred to a beaker containing D-glucose (0.052 g.). The solution was neutralised (barium carbonate), filtered, and concentrated to a thin syrup. The component sugars of this syrup were separated on a filter paper, using solvent A, and the individual sugars eluted with water. The sugars were then estimated quantitatively by oxidising with sodium metaperiodate⁷ and titrating the liberated formic acid with a standard alkali. The results indicate the presence of 98.2% xylose in the xylan. In this estimation, D-ribose could not be used as the reference sugar due to closeness of its migration rate with that of D-xylose.

Methylation of the Xylan.—The xylan (5.6 g.) was methylated nine times with dimethyl sulphate and NaOH according to Chanda *et al.*⁵; yield 3.5 g. This was vigorously shaken for

2 hr. with water (100 ml) and then exhaustively extracted with chloroform in a liquid-liquid extractor for 18 hr. The chloroform was evaporated and the methylated polysaccharide was dried; yield 3.25 g., $[\alpha]_D^{20} - 14.2^\circ$; (c, 0.14 in 10 ml CHCl_3); sulphated ash, 0.42% OMe, 37.1%.

The partly methylated xylan was successively refluxed for 2 hr. (twice each time) with light petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) with increasing concentrations of chloroform⁵. Each fraction was separately dried and weighed. The analytical results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I
Fractionation of the methylated xylan.

Fractions.	CHCl_3 -petroleum.	Yield.	$[\alpha]_D^{20}(\text{CHCl}_3)$.	%OMe.
A	0-100	0.025 g.	..	..
B	10-90	0.040	..	..
C	20-80	0.060	..	..
D	30-70	1.900	-14.6°	37.8
E	40-60	0.700	-14.0°	36.0
F	100-0	0.400	-12.2°	27.8
G	Residue	0.100	..	..

Fraction D was methylated twice with Purdie's reagent; yield 1.65g., $[\alpha]_D^{20} - 14.9^\circ$ (c, 0.09 in 10 ml CHCl_3); OMe, 38.2%. Further methylation of this product with Purdie's reagent did not increase its methoxyl content.

Hydrolysis of the Methylated Xylan.—The methylated polysaccharide (1.5 g.) was subjected to methanolysis with 2% MeOH-HCl and subsequent hydrolysis with *N*-HCl (aqueous). The hydrolysate was worked up in the usual way to provide the methylxyloses in the form of a syrup (yield 1.45 g.). The component sugars of the syrup were separated on a Whatman No. 1 filter paper, using solvent A, and the individual sugars were estimated by the hypiodite-oxidation method of Hirst *et al.*,⁶ using NaOH- Na_3PO_4 buffer⁶. The results are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II
Paper chromatography of the mixture of the methyl sugars.

Spot No.	<i>R_f</i> values.		Possible sugars.	Sugar present.	Molar%.
	Actual.	From tables ¹² .			
1	0.90	0.94	2,3,4-Tri- <i>O</i> -methyl-D-X	1.19 mg.	2.86
2	0.79	0.74	2,3-Di- <i>O</i> -methyl-D-X	38.26	93.70
3*	0.69	0.66	2,4-Di- <i>O</i> -methyl-D-X	0.19	..
4	0.42	0.38	2- <i>O</i> -Methyl-D-X	1.16	3.26
5	0.15	0.15	D-Xylose	0.22	..

X stands for xylopyranose.

*This sugar was not positively identified.

The yield of the trimethylxylose (molar% 2.86) corresponded to one reducing end-group per 35 xylose units in an assumed straight chain.

Separation and Identification of the Methylated Sugars

The syrup containing the mixture of the methylxyloses was resolved into five fractions by paper chromatography on Whatman No. 3 MM filter paper sheets (solvent A). The strips corresponding to the individual sugars were eluted with water and concentrated separately to provide five fractions (I-V).

Fraction I.—Paper chromatography of the syrup (0.039 g.) revealed the presence of a single spot (R_f 0.90; solvent A); $[\alpha]_D^{18} + 19.2^\circ$ (c, 0.039 g. in 10 ml water). It was identified as 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-*D*-xylopyranose by conversion to 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-*N*-phenyl-*D*-xylopyranosylamine, m.p. 99-100° (lit.⁵ m.p. 102°). (Found: OMe, 33.9. $C_{14}H_{21}O_4N$ requires OMe, 34.8%).

Fraction II.—The syrup (1.13 g., R_f 0.76; solvent A) had $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 22.2^\circ$ (c, 0.43 g. in 10 ml water). (Found: OMe, 33.5. $C_7H_{14}O_3$ requires OMe, 34.8%).

The anilide of the sugar, prepared by the method of Hampton *et al.*¹⁰ was crystallised in plates, m.p. 138° (lit.⁵ m.p. 145°); $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 192.3^\circ$ (c, 0.023 g. in 10 ml ethyl acetate). Recrystallisation of the anilide (0.035 g.) yielded colorless shining prisms (0.01g.), m.p. 126°. The 2,3-di-*O*-methyl-*N*-phenyl-*D*-xylopyranosylamine crystallised in two isomorphous forms, one of which melted at 145° and the other at 126°. Both the isomorphs have the same optical rotation of +180° in ethyl acetate¹¹. (Found: OMe, 25.2. $C_{13}H_{19}O_4N$ requires OMe, 24.5%).

Fraction III.—The syrup (0.008 g.) on paper chromatographic examination (solvent A) provided a single spot (R_f 0.69). From the rate of migration it appeared to be 2,4-di-*O*-methyl-*D*-xylopyranose (reported¹² R_f 0.66). The sugar could not be characterised further due to paucity of the material.

Fraction IV.—The syrup (0.044 g.) (R_f 0.40 in solvent A) had $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 34.6^\circ$ (c, 0.019 in 10 ml water). It was characterised as 2-*O*-methyl-*D*-xylopyranose by preparing the crystalline 2-*O*-methyl-*N*-phenyl-*D*-xylopyranosylamine, m.p. 125° (lit.⁵ m.p. 125°); $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 220.4^\circ$ (c, 0.02 in ethyl acetate). (Found: OMe, 12.6. $C_{12}H_{17}O_4N$ requires OMe, 13.0%).

Fraction V.—The syrup (0.008 g.) (R_f 0.15; solvent A) was identified as *D*-xylose from its rate of migration as compared with a known sample in both the solvents A and B for 96 hr. (*p*-anisidine phosphate spray reagent).

Oxidation of the Xylan

(a). *By Hypoiodite Method.*—The xylan (0.10 g.) was oxidised with sodium hypoiodite according to Chanda *et al.*⁵ with the modification that the reaction was carried out for 6 hr. in the dark at 10-12°. From the consumption of the hypoiodite, the average molecular weight and the degree of polymerisation of the xylan were found to be 8800 and 66-67 respectively.

10. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 1739.

11. Ehrenthal *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 1341.

12. Lederer and Lederer, "Chromatography: A Review of Principles and Application", Elsevier Publishing Company, New York, 1953, p. 164.

(b). *By Periodate Method.*—The xylan (0.10 g.) was oxidised with sodium metaperiodate according to the procedure of Halsall *et al.*¹³, as modified by Chanda *et al.*¹⁴. The amount of the liberated formic acid became constant after 168 hr. and corresponded to 1 mole for 17-18 xylose residues. The amount of the periodate consumed at this stage was found to be 1.08 moles for each $C_5H_8O_4$ unit. The uptake of the periodate was estimated by following the procedure described by Fleury and Lange¹⁴.

Degradation of the Periodate-oxidised Xylan

Detection of the Residual Xylose.—The xylan (0.10 g.) was oxidised by sodium metaperiodate for 168 hr. and after elimination of the excess periodate with ethylene glycol¹³, the solution was dialysed for 7 days to remove the inorganic materials and concentrated (5 ml). After addition of 2*N*- H_2SO_4 (5 ml), the solution was hydrolysed in a sealed tube for 12 hr. The clear solution was neutralised (barium carbonate) and concentrated to a thin syrup. Paper chromatographic examination (solvents A and B; *p*-anisidine phosphate) revealed the presence of a faint spot corresponding to D-xylose.

Estimation of the Residual Xylose and Isolation of Pyruvic Acid.—The xylan (0.6 g.) was oxidised with sodium metaperiodate (0.4*M*, 100 ml) for 168 hr. in the dark at 5°. The resulting solution was dialysed for 7 days and concentrated (15 ml). D-Glucose (0.026 g.) and 2*N*- H_2SO_4 (15 ml) were added and the solution was heated in a sealed tube for 16 hr. The hydrolysate was neutralised (barium carbonate) and after being worked up in the usual manner was concentrated and finally dried. The dried product was refluxed with absolute ethanol (2 × 100 ml) for 2 hr. to extract the sugars. The ethanolic extract was filtered and the residual white mass (A) was washed with hot absolute ethanol. The combined filtrate and washings were concentrated to a thin syrup and the amount of the xylose was estimated⁷. The results indicated the presence of 1 mole of xylose for 9150 g. of the xylan. Thus the molecular weight and the D.P. value of the xylan were found to be 9150 and 69-70 respectively.

The residual white mass (A) was dried to remove the last traces of ethanol. It was dissolved in water (25 ml) and passed through freshly regenerated Duolite C-25 cation-exchange resin column (45 × 2.5 cm). The solution was concentrated to about 2 ml. To a portion of the solution (0.5 ml) in a conical flask were added 5% sodium carbonate solution (5 ml) and iodine solution (5 ml) and the mixture was left for 15 min. with occasional shaking. A deep yellow precipitate having the characteristic smell of iodoform was obtained; m.p. 114°. The remaining portion of the solution (1.5 ml) was treated with a solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (0.2 g.) in ethanol (25 ml) containing a few drops of H_2SO_4 (conc.). The mixture was warmed on a water-bath at 60° for 20 min. and left overnight. The 2,4-DNP of pyruvic acid was recrystallised from dry ethyl acetate; m.p. and mixed m.p. 206° (decomp.).

Reduction of the Periodate-oxidised Xylan.—The xylan (0.25 g.) was oxidised with sodium metaperiodate (0.4*M*, 40 ml) for 168 hr., dialysed, and then concentrated (25 ml). Sodium borohydride (0.25 g.) was gradually added to it during 4 hr. with occasional shaking and left overnight. The excess of the borohydride was decomposed (10% acetic acid, 10 ml) and the resulting solution was again dialysed for 7 days. The solution (450 ml)

13. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 1390, 1427.

14. *J. Pharm. Chim.*, 1933, 17, 107, 196.

was concentrated (15 ml), mixed with (3N-H₂SO₄, 15 ml) and heated on a boiling water-bath for 16 hr. The hydrolysate was neutralised (barium carbonate), filtered, and deionised by treating successively with freshly regenerated Duolite C-25 and Duolite A-7 ion-exchange resins. The deionised solution was concentrated to a syrup (0.5ml). Paper chromatographic examination of the syrup, using solvent A and ammoniacal silver nitrate spray reagent, revealed 2 strong spots corresponding to glycerol and glycollic aldehyde and one faint spot corresponding to D-xylose.

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DEPARTMENT OF ORGANIC CHEMISTRY,
NATIONAL SUGAR INSTITUTE,
KANPUR, KANPUR.

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